

Research methodology

Lyophilized blast (Bl) fungal mycelia are nonviable and suitable for international exchange

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In the study of populations of rice Bl fungus *Magnaporthe grisea* (anamorph *Pyricularia grisea*, *P. oryzae*), DNA fingerprinting based on restriction fragment length polymorphism (RFLP) and randomly amplified polymorphic DNA (RAPD) has proved highly informative. Plant pathologists studying Bl recognize the need to analyze populations of the fungus both regionally and worldwide. Unfortunately, relatively few institutions have the necessary resources to perform RFLP and RAPD assays. While collaboration with well-equipped laboratories for comparison of fungal populations seems the ideal solution to limited resources, concern about introducing nonindigenous strains of *M. grisea* into the region of the host

laboratory restricts exchange of fungal isolates.

Purified DNA is currently the only accepted material for international exchange among rice-growing regions. We determined that freeze-dried hyphae of Bl fungus are nonviable and can be safely exchanged instead of pure DNA. We tested the viability of intact lyophilized mycelia (84 samples) and ground lyophilized mycelia (58 samples) from different field strains of *M. grisea*. Hyphal plugs of *M. grisea* were started and grown on modified Fries medium (per liter: 30 g sucrose, 5 g ammonium tartrate, 1 g NH_4NO_3 , 1 g KH_2PO_4 , 0.5 g MgSO_4 , 0.1 g CaCl_2 , 0.1 g NaCl , 0.5 g yeast extract, and 0.5 g casein hydrolysate) dispensed in 50-ml volumes in 125- or 250-ml Erlenmeyer flasks. Flask cultures were shaken for a week at ambient temperature (28-30 °C) on a rotary platform moving at about 150 rpm. Mycelia were continuously submerged and agitated to prevent conidiation.

Mycelia were harvested by suction, rinsed with sterile distilled water, and lyophilized. Dried mycelia were pul-

verized manually under liquid nitrogen. Both intact and ground mycelia were then inoculated onto Fries medium and prune agar plate (per liter of prune infusion: 30-40 g prunes, 5 g lactose, 1 g yeast extract, and 20 g agar), and observed for fungal growth. None of the lyophilized mycelia incubated on either medium for 5 d at 30 °C initiated Bl fungal growth.

We conclude that freeze-dried fungal mycelia are nonviable and therefore suitable for international exchange. For shipment, we recommend that mycelia be packed individually in sterile coin packets and sealed collectively in evacuated plastic bags with activated silica gel or any suitable solid desiccant. Mycelial powders should be wrapped in greased or weighing sheets prior to packing in coin packets to avoid cross-contamination. If kept moisture-tight, mycelia can be stored and shipped at ambient temperatures for at least a week. For long-term storage, we suggest shelving samples at subzero temperatures. Blast researchers for whom DNA extraction is impractical should find the possibility of exchanging lyophilized mycelia particularly useful. ■

An empirical relationship between N input and false smut intensity in rice

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A strong correlation between N input and false smut (*Claviceps oryzae-sativae*) incidence has consistently been reported in the literature. An empirical model that quantitatively describes this relationship might assist in predicting the disease.

We conducted an experiment at RRRS, Punjab Agriculture University, Gudasapur, Punjab, to characterize this relationship. Data were recorded for rice cultivars PR109 and PR106, which were transplanted in 5- × 2-m plots. The experiment

Table 1. Observed (Obs) and predicted (Pred) percent incidence of false smut, RRRS, Punjab Agricultural University, Gurdaspur, Punjab, India.

Cultivar	Nitrogen (kg/ha)	Plants		Tillers		Grains	
		Obs	Pred	Obs	Pred	Obs	Pred
PR109	29	11.4	11.1	14.9	15.9	1.4	1.5
	92	16.2	16.9	22.7	20.9	3.3	3.0
	154	22.9	23.1	29.3	28.6	4.2	4.2
	217	30.5	29.6	36.3	39.0	4.7	5.0
	279	36.2	36.6	53.4	52.1	5.8	5.6
E			0.027		0.060		0.065
R ²			0.996		0.984		0.977
P			<0.01		<0.01		<0.01
PR106	29	8.6	8.9	12.8	12.8	1.3	1.3
	92	14.3	13.4	19.3	19.3	2.0	2.0
	154	18.1	18.5	24.8	24.9	2.5	2.5
	217	23.8	24.1	29.6	29.6	2.9	2.9
	279	30.5	30.3	33.5	33.5	3.2	3.2
E			0.035		0.002		0.006
R ²			0.996		1.0		1.0
P			<0.01		<0.01		<0.01

Table 2. E values for five functions.

Function	PR109			PR106		
	Plants	Tillers	Grains	Plants	Tillers	Grains
$y = mx + c$	0.041	0.085	0.156	0.035	0.039	0.051
$e^y = ax^b$	0.185	0.201	0.054	0.163	0.082	0.063
$y = ab^x$	0.052	0.050	0.202	0.071	0.081	0.087
$y = ax^b$	0.097	0.110	0.056	0.073	0.030	0.018
$y = ax^2 + bx + c$	0.027	0.060	0.065	0.035	0.002	0.006

was laid out in a split-plot design with three replications. Five levels of N were the main plots and cultivars the subplots.

Soil had 29 kg available N/ha, 1.2 kg available P/ha, and 45 kg available K/ha. To compensate for P deficiency and to maintain N levels of 29, 92, 154, 217, and 279 kg/ha, 25 kg P/ha and one-third of the N were applied before puddling. The remaining N was applied equally at 3 and 6 wk after transplanting.

We randomly selected three 1-m² areas in each plot at crop maturity and recorded disease incidence. Percentage of infected plants, tillers, and grains in both cultivars were calculated (Table 1).

Five equations (exponentials: $e^y = ax^b$, $y = ab^x$, $y = ax^b$, and polynomials) were used to describe the relationship between nitrogen (x) and disease incidence (y). Functions were fit to data using standard error or estimate: $E = [(1/N)\sum\{(fp - fo)/$

$fo\}^2]^{1/2}$, where fp (predicted) and fo (observed) are data from N measurements.

E was used to compare regression models (Table 2). A threshold of E = 0.1, which corresponds to an average error of 10% between observed and predicted data, was chosen for selecting the relationship. The best fit was obtained with a quadratic function with error variance of 0.02-0.07.

A quadratic function ($y = ax^2 + bx + c$) was used to predict disease (Table 1). Residuals (9%) were located randomly on both sides of the predicted curve.

For this data set, a quadratic model best described the relationship between N level and false smut intensity. This type of regression model could be used to predict disease incidence provided other conditions match closely. Planners can use these predictions to estimate crop losses. ■

A rapid method for screening rice-associated bacteria antagonistic to *Rhizoctonia solani*

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Screening isolates is an important step in developing biological control agents for *R. solani*, the causal agent of sheath blight (ShB) of rice. We developed a rapid and simple method for screening large numbers of isolates for antagonism to *R. solani*.

Bacterial isolates were isolated and tested for antagonistic effect on *R. solani* by dual culture on potato sucrose agar medium. We used 208 bacterial isolates that strongly inhibited in vitro *R. solani* mycelium growth to determine the effect of seed bacterization. Seeds of mungbean (another host of *R. solani*) and *R. solani* inoculum were spread on sterilized petri dishes. Bacterial suspension was sprayed on each dish. Dishes were kept in a growth chamber.

Damping-off incidence, assessed as percent diseased mungbean plants, was measured 5 d after inoculation. Eighteen of the 288 antagonistic isolates tested reduced damping-off incidence to 50% of that of the control and were considered effective.

The ability of these 18 isolates to protect rice leaves from *R. solani* infection and to restrict lesion expansion was verified with the detached-leaf technique (Rosales et al 1993). Antagonism to infection was tested by spraying rice leaves with bacterial suspension and then placing mycelia discs of *R. solani* on each leaf. Inhibition of lesion expansion was tested by infecting rice leaves with *R. solani* and then spraying bacterial suspension on leaves. We conducted the two experiments in randomized complete block design. Each treatment was replicated three times. Inoculated leaves were incubated in moist chambers at 28-30°C. Lesion length was measured 5 d after applying the bacteria.

Ten of the 18 isolates protected rice leaves from infection, and 11 inhibited ability to inhibit lesion expansion (see table). Further evaluation is needed if

isolates obtained through this rapid screening method reflect biological control ability in the field. Our next step is to test selected isolates in the greenhouse and field to confirm their effectiveness as biological control agents. ■

Lesion length of rice ShB in detached leaf test. Guangzhou, China, 1991.

Bacterial isolate	Lesion length (mm) ^a	
	Antagonism to infection	Inhibition of lesion extension
12542	0 a	1.3 a
Rh71	0 a	2.5 a
RH72	1.7 a	41.0 c
Jinggangmycin ^b	2.3 a	4.2 ab
RH62	4.3 a	2.7 a
11541	7.5 a	24.1 bc
RH921	9.7 a	9.5 ab
RH715	11.7 a	6.0 ab
RH121	15.8 a	8.5 ab
RH22	16.5 a	0.5 a
RH92	17.2 a	6.8 ab
RH131	43.2 b	4.3 ab
9642	45.7 bc	11.0 ab
RH76	51.8 bc	9.2 ab
Check	57.7 bc	30.7 c
8343	67.2 c	39.8 c

^aResults reported are based on two experiments where each treatment was replicated three times. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level by DMRT. ^bAntibiotic made in China.